

TRENDS IN PROVIDING CHEMICAL KNOWLEDGE TO STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16949536>

Annotation: This article highlights the importance of the competency-based approach in teaching chemistry and trends in its effective application. The significance of developing practical knowledge and skills in students through a competency-based approach, enhancing their critical and creative thinking, communication, and teamwork abilities is emphasized. The article also reveals, through real-life examples and experiments, how chemical knowledge can spark students' interest and demonstrate the intrinsic connection between knowledge and life. The process of knowledge acquisition is illustrated through experiments such as "Dry Ice," "Heat Race," "Self-Forming Crystals," and "Canaries in Mines."

Key words: competency-based approach, chemistry education, creative thinking, critical thinking, communication, collaboration, dry ice, practical experience, CO gas, crystallization, STEAM education.

Today, the "competency-based approach" to education has emerged as a new area of research. Competence is derived from the Latin word "compete," which means "I am entering, I am suitable, I am worthy," or refers to knowledge and experience in a particular field. Thus, it indicates that a person has comprehensive knowledge and experience in a certain area. "Competence encompasses knowledge, professional suitability, qualification, experience, and the ability to integrate these into leadership activities."

The Concept for the Development of the Public Education System until 2030 outlines the task of improving teaching methodologies. Currently, preparing students based on the "4K" model, drawing from advanced international experiences, is considered a modern approach. This new approach places greater emphasis on students' critical thinking and their ability to express their opinions freely. This innovative method is aimed at the comprehensive development of children and encompasses four core competencies.

Collaboration - textbooks are structured to foster students' ability to work in teams. This helps students acquire skills in cooperation, effective exchange of ideas, and mutual support.

At this stage, it is advisable to use the competencies we propose in textbooks.

Communicativeness - textbooks are aimed at developing students' ability to communicate with others. Students learn to express their thoughts clearly and

precisely, listen to and understand their interlocutors, and effectively use language tools in conveying information.

Creative thinking - textbooks develop the ability to think creatively and innovate. Students learn to apply new approaches to achieve their goals, develop innovative solutions, and acquire skills in solving creative problems.

"The Trick of Dry Ice"

One summer day, when one of the students approached the store to buy ice cream, he saw a saleswoman placing small pieces of ice on top of the ice creams.

"Wait a moment, little one. Let me put some dry ice on the ice creams," said the seller.

"What did you say? Can ice be dry? We learned in chemistry that water freezes at 0°C to form ice.

But ice can't be dry and hot," he firmly objected to the seller.

"If you don't believe me, here, touch it and see for yourself that it's not dry and hot," said the seller, handing the student a walnut-sized piece of ice. As soon as the student took the ice, his hand burned, and he started passing it from one hand to the other before dropping it. The ice quickly melted and evaporated without leaving any moisture.

"Now, young boy who knows chemistry and physics well, are you convinced that 'dry ice' exists?" said the seller with a laugh.

Task: The student, amazed by this phenomenon, became embarrassed and didn't know what to say. Help your friend! What kind of substance is dry ice? Can there really be hot ice?

Solution: When carbon dioxide gas is cooled to -8°C under a pressure of 60-70 atmospheres, it turns into colorless ice resembling snow. It differs from ordinary ice in that when it melts, it turns into vapor rather than water, and the object it touches does not become wet. That is why it is called "dry ice."

Critical thinking - this methodology involves developing students' skills in critically evaluating information and forming their own opinions and judgments. Students learn to approach problems from an analytical perspective and form their viewpoints based on logical reasoning.

Heat Conductivity Experiment

Below is a quick experiment where you can test how well metals conduct heat compared to non-metals:

First, prepare a cup of hot tea. Then take three spoons made of different materials (plastic, metal, and paper) - one metal, one plastic, and one paper. Place them in hot tea. Then attach all three spoons to a glass filled with ice cubes. You will discover that a metal spoon heats up and cools down faster than a plastic spoon.

Spontaneous crystals

You can form your own crystals using baking soda (NaHCO_3). This experiment will show you how to do it.

1. Fill two jars with hot water. Mix approximately six teaspoons of baking soda in each container. Add more soda until it doesn't melt.
2. Place the dishes in a warm place, place a plate between them. Make sure they don't move.
3. Cut a thread 50 cm long. Attach a paper clip to each end and place one end in each jar.

4. Leave the dishes for at least a week. The crystals should gradually grow along the thread and hang over the plate.

How does this work?

Baking soda is usually sold in the form of a powder consisting of small crystals. The powder dissolves in water. The mixture of water and soda is absorbed with a thread. Then the water slowly flows away and leaves the baking soda - which forms large crystals.

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We know well that miners descend into the depths of the earth to extract coal. The air underground contains various gases that can affect human health. To detect the most dangerous of these gases, miners used to bring cages with canaries down into the mine. As soon as the canaries stopped singing, the miners would ascend from underground.

Task:

Question 1. Which odorless gas has the strongest impact on human health?

- A) methane B) nitrogen (IV) oxide C) propane D) carbon dioxide

Question 2: Which gas did canaries smell faster?

- A) NO B) CH₄ C) CO D) CO₂

Question 3. Choose the answer with the correct air composition?

- A) 78% N, 21% O, 1% additional gases
- B) 78% N, 20% O, 2% associated gases
- C) 77% N, 20% O, 3% associated gases

In conclusion, in today's educational process, teaching students based on a competency-based approach is of particular importance as a modern methodological approach. Especially in chemistry, this approach plays an important role in the formation of students' not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical skills, such necessary competencies as independent thinking, problem-solving, teamwork, and a creative approach.

Through the experiences and real-life examples presented in this article, the possibilities of ensuring interdisciplinary integration and connecting chemistry lessons with life were revealed. This serves to interest students in science, stimulate their critical and creative thinking. In the process of teaching chemistry based on a competency-based approach, teachers should effectively use modern pedagogical methods, transforming students into an active learning subject. As a result, the main goal becomes not the process of acquiring knowledge, but the process of applying knowledge.

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